

Guidance on passport data preparation using Excel: Data cleaning

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About this document

This document is part of a webinar series organized by the Genesys team in 2023 on passport data preparation for publication in Genesys. The series covers practical approaches to data cleaning, standardization to MCPD v.2.1, validation, and eventual publication in Genesys, with a particular focus on genebanks managing passport data in spreadsheets such as Microsoft Excel.

This publication accompanies Part 1 of the series, which focused on data cleaning and preparation of passport data prior to standardization and validation.

This guidance is intended as a practical, step-by-step resource that participants can follow alongside the webinar recording or apply directly to their own datasets.

Webinar resources

Webinar recording:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LBZe4ipO2IE>

Related documents in this series:

Part 2 – Guidance on passport data preparation using Excel: Data standardization

<https://croptrust.box.com/s/zabludc6it46q2vwmufx4uxxtp9hksvh>

Part 3 – Guidance on passport data preparation using Excel: Data validation

<https://croptrust.box.com/s/7hnoxv38qovsfhtu4uqvnyi1doa9xe98>

For questions, support, or to request the sample data file used during the training sessions, please contact: helpdesk@genesys-pgr.org

Guidance on passport data preparation using Excel: Data cleaning

After applying these steps you will be able to prepare your data for validation and standardization to MCPD.

Taxonomy

ORYZA sativa

oryza sativa

Oryza stivvvv

ORYZA Sativa

manihot esculentttt

MANIHOT Esculenta

Manihot ESCULENTA

Solanum lycopersicum

Slanum lycopersicum

Slanum lycopersicum

Slanum lycopersicum

Cleaning

Taxonomy

Oryza sativa

Oryza sativa

Oryza stivvvv

Oryza sativa

Manihot esculentttt

Manihot esculenta

Manihot esculenta

Solanum lycopersicum

Slanum lycopersicum

Slanum lycopersicum

Slanum lycopersicum

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1-Unhide columns

You see that the columns skip from C to F, which means columns D and E are hidden. In order to unhide these columns, **hover** over column C, you will see the mouse turn into an arrow pointing down: ↓

	A	B	C	F	G	H	I
1	Institute	Accession Number	Taxonomy	Biologica	Status in the MLS		Site of safety duplicates
3	A Genebank	OS-103	oryza sativa	Wild	included		IITA
4	A Genebank	OS-104	Oryza spp.	landrace	included		IITA
5	A Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA Sativa	Land Rac	included		IITA
7	A Genebank	OS-107	MANIHOT Esculenta	Landrace	not included		IITA
8	A Genebank	OS-108	Manihot ESCULENTA	improver	not included		IITA
9	A Genebank	OS-108	Solanum Lycopersicum	improver	included		IITA

While hovering over column C and when the down arrow is visible, **click and drag** until column F or G:

	A	B	C	F	G	H	I
1	Institute	Accession Number	Taxonomy	Biologica	Status in the MLS		Site of safety duplicates
3	A Genebank	OS-103	oryza sativa	Wild	included		IITA
4	A Genebank	OS-104	Oryza spp.	landrace	included		IITA
5	A Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA Sativa	Land Rac	included		IITA
7	A Genebank	OS-107	MANIHOT Esculenta	Landrace	not included		IITA
8	A Genebank	OS-108	Manihot ESCULENTA	improver	not included		IITA
9	A Genebank	OS-108	Solanum Lycopersicum	improver	included		IITA

1-Unhide columns

While this column selection is still active, press **right click**. This will open a menu, scroll down to **Unhide** and click it.

	A	B	C	F	H	I
1	Institute	Accession Number	Taxonomy	Biological Status in the MLS		Site of safety duplicates
3	A Genebank	OS-103	oryza sativa	Wild		IITA
4	A Genebank	OS-104	Oryza spp.	landrace		IITA
5	A Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA Sativa	Land Race		IITA
7	A Genebank	OS-107	MANIHOT Esculenta	Landrace		IITA
8	A Genebank	OS-108	Manihot ESCULENTA	improved		IITA
9	A Genebank	OS-108	Solanum lycopersicum	improved		IITA

After clicking Unhide, you will see columns D and E appeared with data about Acquisition date and Collecting source!

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	Institute	Accession Number	Taxonomy	Acquisition date	Collecting source	Biological Status in the MLS		
3	A Genebank	OS-103	oryza sativa	Dec-19	Roadside	Wild	included	
4	A Genebank	OS-104	Oryza spp.	Dec-19	from field	landrace	included	
5	A Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA Sativa	Dec-19	Farmstore	Land Race	included	
7	A Genebank	OS-107	MANIHOT Esculenta	Dec-19	Backyard	Landrace	not included	
8	A Genebank	OS-108	Manihot ESCULENTA	Dec-19	farm store	improved	not included	
9	A Genebank	OS-108	Solanum lycopersicum	Dec-19	farm store	improved	included	

You can do the same to unhide rows!

2-Adjust row sizes

You see that the row sizes are varied, sometimes to the point of making data points invisible.

An easy way to make sure all rows are the same size is first **hover** over the first row until you see the mouse symbol turn into a horizontal arrow: →

While hovering over the first row and the arrow symbol is activated, press a **click** on the mouse. This will select all the arrow.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	Institute	Accession Number	Taxonomy	Acquisition date	Collectin	Biologica	Status in the MLS
3	A Genebank	OS-103	oryza sativa	Dec-19	Roadside	Wild	included
4	A Genebank	OS-104	Oryza spp.	Dec-19	from fiel	landrace	included
5	A Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA Sativa	Dec-19	Farmstor	Land Rac	included

While the arrow selection is active, press on the keyboard at the same time: **Shift Ctr down**. This will select all rows that have data in them.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
10	A Genebank	OS-107	Slanum lycopersicum	Dec-19	farm sto	improvec	included
12	A Genebank	OS-109	slanum lycopersicum	Dec-19	Backya	Landrace	not included
13	A Genebank	OS-110	Slanum lycopersicum	Dec-19	Breeding	Breeding	not included
14	A Genebank	OS-111	Slanum lycopersicum	Dec-19	Breeding	Breeding	not included
15	A Genebank	OS-112	Slanum lycopersicum	Dec-19	Breeding	Breeding	not included
16	A Genebank	OS-112	Slanum lycopersicum	Dec-05	Breeding	Breeding	not included

2-Adjust row sizes

While the selection of all rows is activated, **hover** over the line between two row numbers, for example the line between row 15 and 16, this will turn the mouse symbol into a cross with two arrows:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
10	A Genebank	OS-107	Slanum lycopersicum	Dec-19	farm sto	improvec	included
12	A Genebank	OS-109	Slanum lycopersicum	Dec-19	Backyar	Landrace	not included
13	A Genebank	OS-110	Slanum lycopersicum	Dec-19	Breeding	Breeding	not included
14	A Genebank	OS-111	Slanum lycopersicum	Dec-19	Breeding	Breeding	not included
15	A Genebank	OS-112	Slanum lycopersicum	Dec-19	Breeding	Breeding	not included
16	A Genebank	OS-112	Slanum lycopersicum	Dec-05	Breeding	Breeding	not included

While the cross with two arrows symbol is activated, **double click** on the line between arrows, this will automatically resize all columns to make the data points visible.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	Institute	Accession Number	Taxonomy	Acquisition date	Collectin	Biologica	Status in the MLS
2	A Genebank	OS-102	ORYZA sativa	Dec-19	Field	wild	included
3	A Genebank	OS-103	oryza sativa	Dec-19	Roadside	Wild	included
4	A Genebank	OS-104	Oryza spp.	Dec-19	from fiel	landrace	included
5	A Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA Sativa	Dec-19	Farmstor	Land Rac	included
6	A Genebank	OS-106	manihot esculentttt	Dec-19	Breeding	Breeding	not included
7	A Genebank	OS-107	MANIHOT Esculenta	Dec-19	Backyard	Landrace	not included
8	A Genebank	OS-108	Manihot ESCULENTA	Dec-19	farm sto	improvec	not included
9	A Genebank	OS-108	Solanum lycopersicum	Dec-19	farm sto	improvec	included

You can do the same to resize columns!

You get to the same result in Excel in different ways. For example, you can also adjust row sizes by selecting all rows, right clicking and selecting "Row Height.", then specifying the exact height size. You can do the same to adjust column sizes.

3- Go to last cell

In the Home ribbon, go to "Find & Select" and click on the small arrow that expand its menu.

Once you expand the Find&Select menu, scroll down and click on the "Go to Special..." menu item.

3- Go to last cell

This will open a list of items that Excel can automatically jump to or select. In order to go to the very last cell in your sheet to find potentially hidden data, select **“Last cell”** then click **OK**.

After clicking OK, Excel jumps to a cell in another data table hidden in columns far from your original data.

	CI	CJ	CK	CL	CM	CN	CO	CP	CQ	CR	CS	CT	CU
101	5	December from field	included	A Genebanl	OS-204	Triticum dur	Triticum	durum					
102	5	December Farmstore	included	A Genebanl	OS-205	Triticum dur	Triticum	durum					
103		Jan-12 Breeding ins	not includec	A Genebanl	OS-206	Triticum dur	Triticum	durum					
104		Jan-12 Backyard	not includec	A Genebanl	OS-207	Triticum dur	Triticum	durum					
105	5	December farm store	not includec	A Genebanl	OS-208	Triticum dur	Triticum	durum					
106	5	December farm store	included	A Genebanl	OS-209	Triticum dur	Triticum	durum					
107	7	December farm store	included	A Genebanl	OS-210	Triticum dur	Triticum	durum					
108	3	December farm store	included	A Genebanl	OS-211	Triticum dur	Triticum	durum					
109	3	December Backyard	not includec	A Genebanl	OS-212	Triticum dur	Triticum	durum					
110	10	Decembe Breeding ins	not includec	A Genebanl	OS-213	Triticum dur	Triticum	durum					
111	11	Decembe Breeding ins	not includec	A Genebanl	OS-214	Triticum dur	Triticum	durum					
112	12	Decembe Breeding ins	not includec	A Genebanl	OS-215	Triticum dur	Triticum	durum					
113	13	Decembe Breeding ins	not includec	A Genebanl	OS-216	Triticum dur	Triticum	durum					
114													
115													
116													

Try exploring the other options in the “Go to special” menu items!

4- Review data in notes and comments

Sometimes data corrections are found in notes or comments in Excel, especially if many people are working on the same data file.

In order to visualize all notes at the same time, click on the **Review** ribbon, then expand the **Notes** menu

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Institute	Accession Number	Taxonomy	Acquisition date	Collecting	Biological	Status in the MLS		Site of safety duplicates 1	Site of safety duplicates 2
2	A Genebank	OS-102	ORYZA sativa	Dec-19	Field	wild	included		IITA	Svalbard
3	A Genebank	OS-103	oryza sativa	Dec-19	Roadside	Wild	included		IITA	Svalbard
4	A Genebank	OS-104	Oryza spp.	Dec-19	from fiel	landrace	included		IITA	Svalbard
5	A Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA Sativa	Dec-19	Farmstor	Land Race	included		IITA	Svalbard
6	A Genebank	OS-106	manihot esculenttttt	Dec-19	Breeding	Breeding	not included		IITA	Svalbard
7	A Genebank	OS-107	MANIHOT Esculenta	Dec-19	Backyard	Landrace	not included		IITA	Svalbard
8	A Genebank	OS-108	Manihot ESCULENTA	Dec-19	farm stz	improved	not included		IITA	Svalbard
9	A Genebank	OS-108	Solanum Lycopersicum	Dec-19	farm stz	improved	included		IITA	Svalbard
10	A Genebank	OS-107	Slanum Lycopersicum	Dec-19	farm stz	improved	included		IITA	Svalbard
11	A Genebank	OS-108	Slanum Lycopersicum	Dec-19	farm stz	improved	included		IITA	Svalbard
12	A Genebank	OS-109	Slanum Lycopersicum	Dec-19	Backyard	Landrace	not included		IITA	Svalbard
13	A Genebank	OS-110	Slanum Lycopersicum	Dec-19	Breeding	Breeding	not included		IITA	Svalbard

In the Notes menu, click on **Show all Notes** menu item. This will enable you to visualize all notes at the same time without having to hover above each one.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Institute	Accession Number	Taxonomy	Acquisition date	Collecting	Biological	Status in the MLS		Site of safety duplicates 1	Site of safety duplicates 2
2	A Genebank	OS-102	ORYZA sativa	Dec-19	Field	wild	included		IITA	Svalbard
3	A Genebank	OS-103	oryza sativa	Dec-19	Roadside	Wild	included		IITA	Svalbard
4	A Genebank	OS-104	Oryza spp.	Dec-19	from fiel	landrace	included		IITA	Svalbard
5	A Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA Sativa	Dec-19	Farmstor	Land Race	included		IITA	Svalbard
6	A Genebank	OS-106	manihot esculenttttt	Dec-19	Breeding	Breeding	not included		IITA	Svalbard
7	A Genebank	OS-107	MANIHOT Esculenta	Dec-19	Backyard	Landrace	not included		IITA	Svalbard
8	A Genebank	OS-108	Manihot ESCULENTA	Dec-19	farm stz	improved	not included		IITA	Svalbard
9	A Genebank	OS-108	Solanum Lycopersicum	Dec-19	farm stz	improved	included		IITA	Svalbard
10	A Genebank	OS-107	Slanum Lycopersicum	Dec-19	farm stz	improved	included		IITA	Svalbard
11	A Genebank	OS-108	Slanum Lycopersicum	Dec-19	farm stz	improved	included		IITA	Svalbard
12	A Genebank	OS-109	Slanum Lycopersicum	Dec-19	Backyard	Landrace	not included		IITA	Svalbard
13	A Genebank	OS-110	Slanum Lycopersicum	Dec-19	Breeding	Breeding	not included		IITA	Svalbard

Notes:

- Christelle Rabil: it's actually Oryza sativa
- Christelle Rabil: not sure about it, maybe better to keep blank

4- Review data in notes and comments

In some cases, you may want to correct the data based on their notes, while in other cases you may want to reply to the notes especially if many people are working on the same data file.

However you can only reply to comments in Excel. Therefore you might need to convert your notes into comments. In order to do that, go to the **Review** button, and expand the **Notes** menu, then click on **Convert to Comments**

Institute	Accession Number	Taxonomy	Acquisition date	Collecting Biological	Status in the MLS	Site of safety duplicates 1	Site of safety duplicates 2
A Genebank	OS-102	ORYZA sativa	Dec-19	Field wild	included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-103	oryza sativa	Dec-19	Roadside/Wild	included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-104	Oryza spp.	Dec-19	from field/landrace	included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA Sativa	Dec-19	Farmstore/Land Race	included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-106	manihot esculenttttt	Dec-19	Breeding/Breeding	not included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-107	MANIHOT Esculenta	Dec-19	Backyard/Landrace	not included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-108	Manihot ESCULENTA	Dec-19	farm store improved	not included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-108	Solanum Lycopersicum	Dec-19	farm store improved	not included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-107	Slanum Lycopersicum	Dec-19	farm store improved	included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-108	Slanum Lycopersicum	Dec-19	farm store improved	included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-109	Slanum Lycopersicum	Dec-19	Backyard/Landrace	not included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-110	Slanum lycopersicum	Dec-19	Breeding/Breeding	not included	IITA	Svalbard

You can visualize all comments at the same time by clicking on the Review ribbon, and then **Show Comments** button. Here you can reply, delete or edit comments.

Institute	Accession Number	Taxonomy	Acquisition date	Collecting Biological	Status in the MLS	Site of safety duplicates 1	Site of safety duplicates 2
A Genebank	OS-102	ORYZA sativa	Dec-19	Field wild	included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-103	oryza sativa	Dec-19	Roadside/Wild	included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-104	Oryza spp.	Dec-19	from field/landrace	included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA Sativa	Dec-19	Farmstore/Land Race	included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-106	manihot esculenttttt	Dec-19	Breeding/Breeding	not included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-107	MANIHOT Esculenta	Dec-19	Backyard/Landrace	not included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-108	Manihot ESCULENTA	Dec-19	farm store improved	not included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-108	Solanum Lycopersicum	Dec-19	farm store improved	not included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-107	Slanum Lycopersicum	Dec-19	farm store improved	included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-108	Slanum Lycopersicum	Dec-19	farm store improved	included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-109	Slanum Lycopersicum	Dec-19	Backyard/Landrace	not included	IITA	Svalbard
A Genebank	OS-110	Slanum lycopersicum	Dec-19	Breeding/Breeding	not included	IITA	Svalbard

5- Find invisible data and recolor

Sometimes your data is in an invisible color, for example in white. The cell is not blank but it appears so. In order to spot such cells and recolor them:

In the Home ribbon, go to **“Find & Select”** and click on the small arrow that expand its menu.

The Excel Home ribbon is shown with the 'Find & Select' button highlighted by a yellow box. Below the ribbon is a table with the following data:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	Institute	Accession Number	Taxonomy	Acquisition date	Collectin	Biologica	Sta	
2	A Genebank	OS-102	ORYZA sativa	Dec-19	Field	wild	included	
3	A Genebank	OS-103	oryza sativa	Dec-19	Roadside	Wild	included	
4	A Genebank	OS-104	Oryza spp.	Dec-19	from fiel	landrace	included	
5	A Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA Sativa	Dec-19	Farmstor	Land Rac	included	

Once you expand the Find&Select menu, scroll down and click on the **“Go to Special...”** menu item.

The Excel Home ribbon is shown with the 'Find & Select' menu expanded. The 'Go to Special...' option is highlighted in green, and a hand cursor is pointing to it. Below the ribbon is a table with the following data:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	Institute	Accession Number	Taxonomy	Acquisition date	Collectin	Biologica	Sta	
2	A Genebank	OS-102	ORYZA sativa	Dec-19	Field	wild	inc	
3	A Genebank	OS-103	oryza sativa	Dec-19	Roadside	Wild	inc	
4	A Genebank	OS-104	Oryza spp.	Dec-19	from fiel	landrace	inc	
5	A Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA Sativa	Dec-19	Farmstor	Land Rac	inc	
6	A Genebank	OS-106	manihot esculentttt	Dec-19	Breeding	Breeding not	inc	
7	A Genebank	OS-107	MANIHOT Esculenta	Dec-19	Backyard	Landrace	not included	

5- Find invisible data and recolor

This will open a list of items that Excel can automatically jump to or select. In order to go to the very last cell in your sheet to visualize the cells that are truly blank, regardless whether or not the data is visible, click on **Blanks** then click **OK**.

This will select (in grey) all cells that are completely blank. Notice that column H is not selected, this means that it has data in it that is not visible. Select this column and change the **text color** in the **Home** ribbon.

6- Clearing formats

If your data has many different typographies, colors, text sizes, etc. and you want to unify those, click on the Home ribbon,

In the Home ribbon, expand the Clear menu: then click on **Clear Formats**

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Institute	Accession Nu	Taxonomy	Acquisition	Collecting sou	Biological stat	Status in the C			
2	A Genebank	OS-102	ORYZA sativ	Dec-19	Field	wild	included	ITA003	IITA	Site of safety duplicates 2
3	A Genebank	OS-103	oryza sativa	Dec-19	Roadside	Wild	included	ITA004	IITA	Svalbard
4	A Genebank	OS-104	Oryza sativa	Dec-19	from field	landrace	included	ITA005	IITA	Svalbard
5	A Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA Sativ	Dec-19	Farmstore	Land Race	included	ITA006	IITA	Svalbard
6	A Genebank	OS-106	manihot escul	Dec-19	Breeding institute	Breeding material	not included	ITA007	IITA	Svalbard
7	A Genebank	OS-107	MANIHOT I	Dec-19	Backyard	Landrace	not included	ITA008	IITA	Svalbard
8	A Genebank	OS-108	Manihot ESC	Dec-19	farm store	improved cultivar		ITA009	IITA	Svalbard
9	A Genebank	OS-108	Solanum lycopersicum	Dec-19	farm store	improved cultivar	included	ECU001	IITA	Svalbard

Clearing formats will automatically standardize text sizes, fonts, colors, etc.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Institute	Accession Number	Taxonomy	Acquisition date	Collecting source	Biological status	Status in the MLS	Collecting institute code	Site of safety duplicates 1	Site of safety duplic
2	A Genebank	OS-102	ORYZA sativa	43830	Field	wild	included	ITA003	IITA	Svalbard
3	A Genebank	OS-103	oryza sativa	43830	Roadside	Wild	included	ITA004	IITA	Svalbard
4	A Genebank	OS-104	Oryza sativa	43830	from field	landrace	included	ITA005	IITA	Svalbard
5	A Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA Sativa	43830	Farmstore	Land Race	included	ITA006	IITA	Svalbard
6	A Genebank	OS-106	manihot esculentttt	43830	Breeding institute	Breeding material	not included	ITA007	IITA	Svalbard
7	A Genebank	OS-107	MANIHOT Esculenta	43830	Backyard	Landrace	not included	ITA008	IITA	Svalbard
8	A Genebank	OS-108	Manihot ESCULENTA	43830	farm store	improved cultivar		ITA009	IITA	Svalbard
9	A Genebank	OS-108	Solanum lycopersicum	43830	farm store	improved cultivar	included	ECU001	IITA	Svalbard
10	A Genebank	OS-107	Slanum lycopersicum	43830	farm store	improved cultivar	included	ECU001	IITA	Svalbard
11	A Genebank	OS-108	Slanum lycopersicum	43830	farm store	improved cultivar	included	ECU001	IITA	Svalbard
12	A Genebank	OS-109	Slanum lycopersicum	43830	Backyard	Landrace	not included	ECU001	IITA	Svalbard
13	A Genebank	OS-110	Slanum lycopersicum	43830	Breeding institute	Breeding material	not included	ECU001	IITA	Svalbard
14	A Genebank	OS-111	Slanum lycopersicum	43830	Breeding institute	Breeding material	not included	ECU001	IITA	Svalbard

After clearing formats, notice the Acquisition date column changed from "Dec-19" to the number 43830. This is because Excel processes dates as numbers after the day 01 January 1900. We will address date formats at later steps.

7- Create an Excel Table

To make managing and analyzing a group of related data easier, you can turn a range of cells into an Excel table (previously known as an Excel list).

To quickly create a table in Excel, do the following: select all your data by clicking at the same time **Ctrl A**

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Institute	Accession Number	Taxonomy	Acquisition date	Collecting source	Biological status	Status in the MLS	Collecting institute code	Site of safety duplicates 1	Site of safety duplicates 2
2	A Genebank	OS-102	ORYZA sativa	43830	Field	wild	included	ITA003	IITA	Svalbard
3	A Genebank	OS-103	oryza sativa	43830	Roadside	Wild	included	ITA004	IITA	Svalbard
4	A Genebank	OS-104	Oryza sativa	43830	from field	landrace	included	ITA005	IITA	Svalbard
5	A Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA Sativa	43830	Farmstore	Land Race	included	ITA006	IITA	Svalbard
6	A Genebank	OS-106	manihot esculenttttt	43830	Breeding institute	Breeding material	not included	ITA007	IITA	Svalbard
7	A Genebank	OS-107	MANIHOT Esculenta	43830	Backyard	Landrace	not included	ITA008	IITA	Svalbard
8	A Genebank	OS-108	Manihot ESCULENTA	43830	farm store	improved cultivar		ITA009	IITA	Svalbard
9	A Genebank	OS-108	Solanum lycopersicum	43830	farm store	improved cultivar	included	ECU001	IITA	Svalbard
10	A Genebank	OS-107	Slanum lycopersicum	43830	farm store	improved cultivar	included	ECU001	IITA	Svalbard
11	A Genebank	OS-108	Slanum lycopersicum	43830	farm store	improved cultivar	included	ECU001	IITA	Svalbard
12	A Genebank	OS-109	Slanum lycopersicum	43830	Backyard	Landrace	not included	ECU001	IITA	Svalbard
13	A Genebank	OS-110	Slanum lycopersicum	43830	Breeding institute	Breeding material	not included	ECU001	IITA	Svalbard
14	A Genebank	OS-111	Slanum lycopersicum	43830	Breeding institute	Breeding material	not included	ECU001	IITA	Svalbard
15	A Genebank	OS-112	Slanum lycopersicum	43830	Breeding institute	Breeding material	not included	ECU001	IITA	Svalbard
16	A Genebank	OS-112	Slanum lycopersicum	38717	Breeding institute	Breeding material	not included	ECU001	IITA	Svalbard

While all your data is selected, type on the keyboard at the same time **Ctrl T** then click **OK**

Where is the data for your table?
=\$A\$1:\$M\$16
 My table has headers
Cancel OK

If you titled these columns, then make sure to tick this box.

You can find more information on Excel tables in this link:

<https://support.microsoft.com/en-gb/office/overview-of-excel-tables-7ab0bb7d-3a9e-4b56-a3c9-6c94334e492c>

8- Splitting one column into two

Sometimes you need to split one column into two or many as part of the data cleaning process. Let's take an example the Taxonomy column below being split into two columns: Genus and Species.

First, determine how many columns you want to split up your original column into, in this example it's two. Then add two columns to your table, right after the Taxonomy column. **Right click** and **Insert Table Columns to the Left**.

	B	C	D	E	F	G	
1	Accession Number	Taxonomy	Acquisition date	Collecting source	Biological status	Status in the MLS	Collecting
2	DS-102	ORYZA sativa			wild	included	ITA003
3	DS-103	oryza sativa			Wild	included	ITA004
4	DS-104	Oryza sativa			landrace	included	ITA005
5	DS-105	ORYZA Sativa			Land Race	included	ITA006
6	DS-106	manihot esculenttttt			institute	Breeding material	ITA007
7	DS-107	MANIHOT Esculenta				not included	ITA008
8	DS-108	Manihot ESCULENTA				not included	ITA009
9	DS-108	Solanum lycopersicum			improved	included	ECU001
10	DS-107	Slanum lycopersicum			improved cultivar	included	ECU001
11	DS-108	Slanum lycopersicum			improved cultivar	included	ECU001
12	DS-109	Slanum lycopersicum			Landrace	not included	ECU001
13	DS-110	Slanum lycopersicum			institute	Breeding material	ECU001
14	DS-111	Slanum lycopersicum			institute	Breeding material	ECU001
15	DS-112	Slanum lycopersicum			institute	Breeding material	ECU001
16	DS-112	Slanum lycopersicum			institute	Breeding material	ECU001

Rename the new columns to Genus and Species. Then, **select all the Taxonomy column** click on the first row, then type simultaneously **Ctrl Shift down**.

	B	C	D	E	F	G	
1	Accession Number	Taxonomy	Genus	Species	Acquisition date	Collecting source	Biological
2	DS-102	ORYZA sativa			43830	Field	wild
3	DS-103	oryza sativa			43830	Roadside	Wild
4	DS-104	Oryza sativa			43830	from field	landrace
5	DS-105	ORYZA Sativa			43830	Farmstore	Land Race
6	DS-106	manihot esculenttttt			43830	Breeding institute	Breeding r
7	DS-107	MANIHOT Esculenta			43830	Backyard	Landrace
8	DS-108	Manihot ESCULENTA			43830	farm store	improved
9	DS-108	Solanum lycopersicum			43830	farm store	improved
10	DS-107	Slanum lycopersicum			43830	farm store	improved
11	DS-108	Slanum lycopersicum			43830	farm store	improved
12	DS-109	Slanum lycopersicum			43830	Backyard	Landrace
13	DS-110	Slanum lycopersicum			43830	Breeding institute	Breeding r
14	DS-111	Slanum lycopersicum			43830	Breeding institute	Breeding r

8- Splitting one column into two

Then, copy the data from the Taxonomy column by typing **Ctrl C**, and paste it in the Genus column by typing **Ctrl V**.

	B	C	D	E	F	G	
1	Accession Number	Taxonomy	Genus	Species	Acquisition date	Collecting source	Biologi
2	DS-102	ORYZA sativa	ORYZA sativa		43830	Field	wild
3	DS-103	oryza sativa	oryza sativa		43830	Roadside	Wild
4	DS-104	Oryza sativa	Oryza sativa		43830	from field	landrac
5	DS-105	ORYZA Sativa	ORYZA Sativa		43830	Farmstore	Land R
6	DS-106	manihot esculenttttt	manihot esculenttttt		43830	Breeding institute	Breedi
7	DS-107	MANIHOT Esculenta	MANIHOT Esculenta		43830	Backyard	Landra
8	DS-108	Manihot ESCULENTA	Manihot ESCULENTA		43830	farm store	improv
9	DS-108	Solanum lycopersicum	Solanum lycopersicum		43830	farm store	improv
10	DS-107	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum lycopersicum		43830	farm store	improv
11	DS-108	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum lycopersicum		43830	farm store	improv
12	DS-109	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum lycopersicum		43830	Backyard	Landra
13	DS-110	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum lycopersicum		43830	Breeding institute	Breedi
14	DS-111	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum lycopersicum		43830	Breeding institute	Breedi
15	DS-112	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum lycopersicum		43830	Breeding institute	Breedi
16	DS-112	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum lycopersicum		38717	Breeding institute	Breedi

Then select all the data in the Genus column by clicking on the first row and typing simultaneously **Shift Ctrl down**.

While keeping the Genus column selected, click on the **Data** ribbon, then click on the **Text to Column** button:

The screenshot shows the Microsoft Excel interface. The 'Data' ribbon is active, and the 'Text to Columns' button is highlighted with a yellow box and a hand cursor. Below the ribbon, the spreadsheet is visible, with the 'Genus' column (column D) selected. The data in the spreadsheet is identical to the table shown in the previous image.

8- Splitting one column into two

Clicking on Text to Column will start a dialog box composed of 3 steps that allows you at the end to split your selected data into two columns.

If your data is delimited by a space, comma or any other character then click on Delimited in step 1. In step 2 you select what is the separator of the two columns, in our case it is a space. In step 3 click on Finish.

Now you can see the genus names and the species names split into two columns! Read more on the Text to Column in

<https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/office/split-text-into-different-columns-with-the-convert-text-to-columns-wizard-30b14928-5550-41f5-97ca-7a3e9c363ed7>

	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
	Accession Number	Taxonomy	Genus	Species	Acquisition date	Collecting source	Biolog
2	DS-102	ORYZA sativa	ORYZA	sativa	43830	Field	wild
3	DS-103	oryza sativa	oryza	sativa	43830	Roadside	Wild
4	DS-104	Oryza sativa	Oryza	sativa	43830	from field	landrac
5	DS-105	ORYZA Sativa	ORYZA	Sativa	43830	Farmstore	Land R.
6	DS-106	manihot esculenttttt	manihot	esculenttttt	43830	Breeding institute	Breedii
7	DS-107	MANIHOT Esculenta	MANIHOT	Esculenta	43830	Backyard	Landra
8	DS-108	Manihot ESCULENTA	Manihot	ESCULENTA	43830	farm store	improv
9	DS-108	Solanum lycopersicum	Solanum	lycopersicum	43830	farm store	improv
10	DS-107	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum	lycopersicum	43830	farm store	improv
11	DS-108	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum	lycopersicum	43830	farm store	improv
12	DS-109	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum	lycopersicum	43830	Backyard	Landra
13	DS-110	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum	lycopersicum	43830	Breeding institute	Breedii
14	DS-111	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum	lycopersicum	43830	Breeding institute	Breedii
15	DS-112	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum	lycopersicum	43830	Breeding institute	Breedii
16	DS-112	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum	lycopersicum	38717	Breeding institute	Breedii

9- Change cases for case-sensitive data

If you want your text to have the first letter capitalized, and the remaining letters in lower case (for example for the genus name), use the **PROPER** function.

First add a table column next to Genus: **Right click** and **Insert Table Columns to the Left**.

Number	Taxonomy	Genus	Species	Acquisition date	Collecting source	Biological
2	ORYZA sativa	ORYZA	sativa	43830	Field	wildc
3	oryza sativa	oryza	sativa	43830	Roadside	Wild
4	Oryza sativa	Oryza	sativa	43830	from field	land
5	ORYZA Sativa	ORYZA	Sativa	43830	Farmstore	Land
6	manihot esculenttttt	manihot	escul	43830	Breeding institute	Bre
7	MANIHOT Esculenta	MANIHOT	Escul	43830	farm	Land
8	Manihot ESCULENTA	Manihot	ESCU	43830	farm store	imp
9	Solanum lycopersicum	Solanum	lycop	43830	farm store	imp
10	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum	lycop	43830	farm store	imp
11	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum	lycop	43830	farm store	imp
12	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum	lycop	43830	Backyard	Land
13	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum	lycop	43830	Breeding institute	Bre
14	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum	lycop	43830	Breeding institute	Bre
15	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum	lycop	43830	Breeding institute	Bre
16	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum	lycop	38717	Breeding institute	Bre

It is recommended to keep the original column by adding the word "original" to its name, for later quality checks. So in this example, we **rename** "Genus" to "Genus_original" and name the newly added column "GENUS".

Number	Taxonomy	Genus original	GENUS	Species	Acquisition date	Co
2	ORYZA sativa	ORYZA		sativa	43830	Fie
3	oryza sativa	oryza		sativa	43830	Ro
4	Oryza sativa	Oryza		sativa	43830	fro
5	ORYZA Sativa	ORYZA		Sativa	43830	Far
6	manihot esculenttttt	manihot		esculenttttt	43830	Bre
7	MANIHOT Esculenta	MANIHOT		Esculenta	43830	Bac
8	Manihot ESCULENTA	Manihot		ESCULENTA	43830	fari
9	Solanum lycopersicum	Solanum		lycopersicum	43830	fari
10	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum		lycopersicum	43830	fari
11	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum		lycopersicum	43830	fari
12	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum		lycopersicum	43830	Bac
13	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum		lycopersicum	43830	Bre
14	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum		lycopersicum	43830	Bre
15	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum		lycopersicum	43830	Bre
16	Slanum lycopersicum	Slanum		lycopersicum	38717	Bre

9- Change cases for case-sensitive data

To apply the PROPER function, make sure you press on the first cell of the newly added column titled GENUS, then in the functions bar, type **=PROPER(**

Then press on the cell with the original genus name, in this example it is D2, then close the parentheses and press enter. Our final formula is **=PROPER([@[Genus original]])** because we are working in an Excel table.

member	Taxonomy	Genus original	GENUS	species
	ORYZA sativa	ORYZA	=PROPER([@[Genus original]])	
	oryza sativa	oryza		ativa
	Oryza sativa	Oryza		ativa
	ORYZA Sativa	ORYZA		ativa
	manihot esculenttttt	manihot		sculenttttt
	MANIHOT Esculenta	MANIHOT		sculenta
	Manihot ESCULENTA	Manihot		SCULENTA

After pressing Enter, and because we are working in a table, Excel will populate all the new column with this function, thus converting your text into the first letter capitalized, and the remaining letters in lower case.

Apply the same for the Species column by using **LOWER** function!

En **français**: PROPER est NOMPROPRE and LOWER est MINUSCULE

En **inglés**: PROPER esNOMPROPIO and LOWER es MINUSC

10- Erase leading and trailing spaces

To remove all additional spaces from your text except for single spaces between words, use **TRIM** function on your original data that may have irregular spacing.

Apply the same steps as indicated previously in section number 9, but instead of using the PROPER function, type **TRIM**.

member	Taxonomy	Genus original	GENUS	Species
	ORYZA sativa	ORYZA	ORYZA	sativa
	oryza sativa	oryza	oryza	sativa
	Oryza sativa	Oryza	Oryza	sativa
	ORYZA Sativa	ORYZA	ORYZA	Sativa
	manihot esculenttttt	manihot	manihot	esculenttttt
	MANIHOT Esculenta	MANIHOT	MANIHOT	Esculenta
	Manihot ESCULENTA	Manihot	Manihot	ESCULENTA
	Solanum lycopersicum	Solanum	Solanum	lycopersicum

En **français**: TRIM est SUPPRESSESPACE

En **inglés**: TRIM es ESPACIOS

Instead of using two functions separately, you may use them in combination, for example you may type:

=TRIM(PROPER(A2))

But when you use a combination of functions, please make sure to close all parentheses

11- Disconnect data from function

After applying any function to a column, for example in the previous step 9, this column will become linked to the original data.

If you delete the original Genus column, your new GENUS column will show values as an error: **#REF!**

The diagram illustrates the process of disconnecting data from a function. On the left, a table with two columns, 'Genus original' and 'GENUS', is shown. The 'Genus original' column is highlighted with a yellow border and a large yellow 'X' over it, indicating it is being deleted. A yellow arrow points from the 'GENUS' column of this table to a second table on the right. This second table, titled 'GENUS', shows the result of the deletion: all cells in the column now contain the error '#REF!'.

Genus original	GENUS
ORYZA	ORYZA
manihot	manihot
MANIHOT	MANIHOT
Manihot	Manihot
Solanum	Solanum

GENUS
#REF!

In order to avoid that, you may disconnect the data in the GENUS column from the function by applying the following steps:

Select all the data in the GENUS column by clicking on the first cell, then **Ctrl Shift down**

Genus original	GENUS
ORYZA	ORYZA
manihot	manihot
MANIHOT	MANIHOT
Manihot	Manihot
Solanum	Solanum

11- Disconnect data from function

While your selection of the GENUS data is active, copy the data by pressing **Ctrl C**, then go to the Home ribbon and press on **Paste Values**:

Now you have disconnected your values from the function, and in case you delete your original column, there won't be any **#REF!** error replacing your data.

Setting up the Excel functions translator

If you use Excel in any other language than English, some functions and tools might be named differently than in this guide. Microsoft created a plug-in that you can add to your Excel in order to help with translations of functions.

Please refer to the following article to set up the Functions Translator in Excel:

<https://support.microsoft.com/en-gb/office/excel-functions-translator-f262d0c0-991c-485b-89b6-32cc8d326889>

This guide complements the webinar on Passport Data Preparation Part 1. Stay tuned for the following parts that will cover data validation and mapping to MCPD. If you have any questions about these steps, please send an email to helpdesk@genesys-pgr.org

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